

A layerwise plate element formulation with adhesive interface compliance and thermal loads for bonded multilayer structures

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Novel layerwise finite element formulation for adhesively bonded multilayer plates.
- Adhesive layers are included as shear-only interfaces with defined stiffness and thickness.
- Suitable for highly heterogeneous layer stacks (e.g., hybrid laminates, sandwich constructions).

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel layerwise plate finite element formulation for the modelling of adhesively bonded multilayer structures subjected to thermal loading. Each structural layer is represented as a Reissner–Mindlin plate, while interlayer coupling is achieved through adhesive shear layers with defined thickness and shear stiffness. This approach enables the direct representation of adhesive compliance, which is often simplified or neglected in layerwise plate formulations. The formulation is derived via the principle of virtual work and incorporates mixed interpolation of tensorial components to prevent shear locking. Numerical examples demonstrate the accuracy and computational efficiency of the proposed element. Comparisons with three-dimensional solid finite element reference models show good agreement with the computed deflections, while requiring substantially fewer degrees of freedom. The resulting computational efficiency makes the approach particularly attractive for iterative analyses such as process simulations and parametric studies involving thermally induced deformations. Since the adhesive shear modulus enters the formulation only as a parameter, time- or temperature-dependent behaviour can be incorporated through constitutive modelling without modification of the element formulation.

1. Introduction

Bonded multilayer structures are widely used in various engineering fields. The mechanical response of such structures depends not only on the stiffness of the individual layers but also on the compliance of the adhesive interfaces that transmit shear between layers. Accurate and efficient modelling of these interfaces is therefore essential for predicting global deformation and performance.

Finite element modelling strategies for multilayer structures can be broadly divided into beam, shell or plate and solid element approaches. While beam formulations are well established for slender one-dimensional structures, they are not applicable to surfaces exhibiting curvature in two directions. Beam formulations are therefore not considered here, leaving plate- and solid-type approaches as suitable

modelling strategies for the intended application. Three-dimensional finite element solid models (SM) resolve each layer and adhesive explicitly. This enables detailed prediction of stresses, including interlaminar and edge effects, and allows straightforward incorporation of time- and temperature-dependent material laws. However, the price of this accuracy is a large number of degrees of freedom (DOF), making SM computationally expensive and often impractical for iterative simulations such as parametric studies or process modelling.

Plate- and shell-based approaches for multilayer structures are further divided by Reddy into two main categories [1]: Equivalent single layer (ESL) and layerwise (LW) theories. ESL theories try to formulate a single layer with properties equal to that of the whole multilayer structure. This makes them computationally efficient. However, an

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assumption must be made as to how displacements vary through the thickness of the plate. This becomes difficult when trying to account for relative displacements between structural layers in the case of low adhesive shear modulus or even completely unbonded layers. The well known classical plate theory is the simplest ESL formulation. It is applicable to thin plates, whereas for thick and multilayer plates higher order shear deformation theories have been developed, over which an overview is given by Abrate and Di Scuvia [2].

LW theories provide an intermediate approach. They apply single-layer theory at the layer level and ensure displacement continuity via inter-laminar relationships. A systematic framework for deriving both ESL and LW theories is provided by the Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF) [3]. By expressing the displacement field through a hierarchical expansion in the thickness direction, CUF enables the generation of different kinematic assumptions within a unified formalism. This approach is particularly powerful for developing refined LW models capable of accurately capturing out-of-plane stresses, which can be critical in the analysis of thick multilayered structures.

While CUF offers a high degree of generality, the present work adopts a problem-driven layer-by-layer formulation based on coupled Reissner–Mindlin plates. This choice is motivated by the primary focus on explicitly modelling compliant adhesive interfaces via a variable-stiffness approach, which provides the required kinematic flexibility for efficient process simulation without introducing additional hierarchical DOF that are not essential for the intended application. The attractiveness of LW formulations stems from their computational efficiency compared to SM approaches and their greater kinematic flexibility compared to ESL theories, particularly in the presence of inter-layer slip. Still, most of the LW theories assume perfect bonding at the interfaces. A detailed overview of LW-formulations can be found in Ref. [4]. Shell and plate elements allowing for inter-layer slip were derived among others by Krawczyk [5], Park et al. [6], Nguyen et al. [7] and Erturk and Tekinalp [8]. However, these formulations either neglect shear deformation of the structural layers, ignore the finite thickness of the adhesive, or both. While these assumptions are valid for some cases, they limit applicability when adhesive compliance and shear deformation of structural layers are significant.

Magisano et al. recently presented a formulation for alternating stiff/soft layups that enriches a Kirchhoff–Love shell model by means of through-the-thickness warping functions [9]. Their results demonstrate that high accuracy with respect to SM reference solutions can be achieved when independent transverse shear deformations are introduced for the soft layers. When the soft interlayers are uniform in terms of thickness and stiffness, the warping of these layers can be represented by a single zigzag function without loss of accuracy, rendering the number of DOF independent of the number of layers and resulting in a highly efficient model. Modelling the stiff layers as Kirchhoff–Love shells is an assumption also adopted in other recent formulations [10] and is appropriate for many technical applications involving alternating layups of clearly distinguishable stiff and soft layers, where transverse shear strains in the stiff layers can be neglected.

The present work introduces a new LW plate element, denoted LW-VISPE4 (Layerwise Variable Interface Stiffness Plate Element with four nodes), which targets the efficient prediction of thermally induced global deformations in process-oriented simulations of adhesively bonded multilayer structures, in which differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion between layers introduce significant shear strains. The structural layers, whose stiffness may differ by several orders of magnitude, are modelled as Reissner–Mindlin plates. Adjacent layers are coupled through shear-only adhesive layers characterized by their shear modulus and thickness. This permits modelling of adhesive layers across a wide range of stiffness values, from uncured to fully cured states. The adhesive thickness also contributes to the total laminate thickness, thereby affecting the global bending stiffness. Thermal strains are incorporated at the layer level and enter the variational formulation alongside

the mechanical strains. Together, these features define the scope of the proposed formulation.

These features and modelling decisions are motivated by the intended application to process simulations of alpine ski manufacturing, where relatively thick adhesive layers are used and the comparably soft core, sandwiched between stiffer top and bottom layers, undergoes significant shear deformation. Assuming an initial flat reference surface and limiting the analysis to small deformations, this approach is also applicable to a range of similar multilayer plate problems characterized by compliant interfaces. For context, the ski manufacturing process is briefly outlined in the following paragraph.

Alpine skis are typical sandwich structures, usually consisting of a wooden core with multiple top and bottom layers made from different materials, each specifically chosen to influence certain properties of the ski (e.g. stiffness, damping)[11]. Both the experimental determination of these properties [12,13] and their prediction using finite element models [14,15] are well established. Less studied is how these properties, particularly the camber profile, are generated during manufacturing. In the manufacturing process, all layers are impregnated with adhesive before being stacked and heat pressed. In the press, the ski is heated up to a certain temperature, depending on the type of adhesive. The ski is held at that temperature to let the adhesive cure before being cooled back down to room temperature. As the layers are essentially unbonded during the heating phase, but bonded while cooling down, the different coefficients of thermal expansion of each layer lead to deformation of the ski. Such cure induced deformations of multilayer structures have been studied by various researchers. The focus of this research is usually on the formulation of an appropriate material model for the adhesive (which will not be addressed in this paper), which is then implemented in a continuum finite element based simulation (e.g. [16–18]). Based on this approach, Hauenstein et al. have developed a thermo-mechanical model of the ski manufacturing process [19]. This SM resolves each layer and interface in detail and showed great predictive capability, but its high computational cost made it impractical for design optimization applications outside of an academic setting. The development of LW-VISPE4 is a first step towards an efficient alternative.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the element formulation. In Section 3 the results for different numerical examples are compared to SM results. Finally, conclusions are presented in Section 4.

2. Layerwise variable interface stiffness plate element

In this section the formulation of a novel layerwise plate element (LW-VISPE4) subjected to thermal loads is derived based on the principle of virtual work and under the assumption of small deformations. LW element formulations are developed by applying single layer element formulations at the layer level. These plate layers, hereinafter referred to as structural layers, are a superposition of a flat bilinear isoparametric Reissner–Mindlin plate element [20,21] and a common plane stress membrane element. The key contribution of this work is the coupling of the individual structural layers via an adhesive shear layer, for which the shear strain is calculated directly from the nodal values of the adjacent structural layers (Fig. 1). It is assumed, that the adhesive layer’s membrane stiffness can be neglected, which is the case for low stiffness of the adhesive compared to the structural layers. The total internal virtual work can be formulated as the sum of the virtual work in the structural and the adhesive layers as follows

$$\delta W^{(e)} = \delta W_s^{(e)} + \delta W_a^{(e)} \\ = \sum_{l=1}^n \left(\int_{\Omega_s^l} \delta \epsilon^{lT} \sigma^l d\Omega_s^l + \int_{\Omega_s^l} \delta \gamma^{lT} \tau^l d\Omega_s^l \right) + \sum_{l=1}^{n-1} \int_{\Omega_a^l} \delta \gamma_a^{lT} \tau_a^l d\Omega_a^l \quad (1)$$

The superscript (e) denotes quantities related to the element, while the superscript l is used to denote nodal values or properties related to

Fig. 1. Structural lay-up and nodal values of the LW plate element.

individual layers. Where necessary for clarity, subscripts s and a are used to distinguish between structural and adhesive layer quantities respectively.

2.1. Kinematics of the structural layers

With the assumptions of Reissner-Mindlin theory the displacement field within each layer l is given by

$$\begin{aligned} u^l &= u_0^l(x, y) + z^l \varphi_y(x, y) \\ v^l &= v_0^l(x, y) - z^l \varphi_x(x, y) \\ w &= w(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where z^l is the distance measured from the mid-plane of each individual layer. The strains and stresses for layer l can then be expressed by

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon^l &= \epsilon_0^l - z \varphi^{l'} \\ \gamma^l &= \mathbf{w}' - \varphi^l \\ \sigma^l &= \mathbf{C}^l (\epsilon^l - \alpha^l \Delta T^l) \\ \tau^l &= \mathbf{C}_s^l \cdot \gamma^l \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_0^l is the vector of layer mid-surface strains, γ^l is the shear angle vector, φ^l is the cross-section rotation and $\varphi^{l'}$ represents the derivatives thereof, as does \mathbf{w}' for the vertical deflection.

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_0^l &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_0^l}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0^l}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u_0^l}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0^l}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} & \varphi^{l'} &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\partial \varphi_y^l}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_x^l}{\partial y} \\ -\frac{\partial \varphi_y^l}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \varphi_x^l}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \\ \varphi^l &= \begin{bmatrix} -\varphi_y^l \\ \varphi_x^l \end{bmatrix} & \mathbf{w}' &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

\mathbf{C}^l and \mathbf{C}_s^l are the layer's orthotropic elasticity matrices, divided into a membrane and shear part (Appendix A). The transverse shear behaviour is modelled using the mixed interpolation of tensorial components (MITC) approach [22], which is known to alleviate shear locking in low-order plate and shell elements and has also been demonstrated to be effective in multilayer plate formulations [23,24].

Inserting these definitions into the formulation of the internal virtual work of the structural layers yields

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W_s^l &= \int_{\Omega^l} (\delta \epsilon_0^l - z \delta \varphi^{l'})^T \mathbf{C}^l (\epsilon_0^l - z \varphi^{l'} - \alpha^l \Delta T^l) d\Omega^l \\ &+ \int_{\Omega^l} (\delta \mathbf{w}' - \delta \varphi^l)^T \mathbf{C}_s^l (\mathbf{w}' - \varphi^l) d\Omega^l \\ &= \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} \delta \epsilon_0^{lT} \mathbf{C}^l \epsilon_0^l d\Omega^l}_{(1)} - \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} \delta \epsilon_0^{lT} \mathbf{C}^l z \varphi^{l'} d\Omega^l}_{(2)} \\ &- \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} z \delta \varphi^{l'T} \mathbf{C}^l \epsilon_0^l d\Omega^l}_{(3)} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} \delta \varphi^{l'T} \mathbf{C}^l z^2 \varphi^{l'} d\Omega^l}_{(4)} \\ &- \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} \delta \epsilon_0^{lT} \mathbf{C}^l \alpha^l \Delta T^l d\Omega^l}_{(5)} + \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} z \delta \varphi^{l'T} \mathbf{C}^l \alpha^l \Delta T^l d\Omega^l}_{(6)} \\ &+ \underbrace{\int_{\Omega^l} (\delta \mathbf{w}' - \delta \varphi^l)^T \mathbf{C}_s^l (\mathbf{w}' - \varphi^l) d\Omega^l}_{(7)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The first integral yields the membrane stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_m^l . The fourth and seventh integrals yield the bending \mathbf{K}_b^l and shear stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_s^l respectively. Integrals five and six yield the thermal load vectors, which will be detailed in a separate section. The second and third integrals vanish due to the symmetric integration of the linear z -terms over the layer thickness with respect to the layer mid-plane.

2.2. Kinematics of the adhesive layers

To describe the contribution of the adhesive layers to the total virtual work (the second term in Eq. (1)), the kinematics of the adhesive layers must be derived (Fig. 2). The horizontal displacement of the layer l top surface and the layer $l + 1$ bottom surface in the x -direction are

$$\begin{aligned} u_t^l &= u_0^l + \varphi_y^{l'} \frac{t^l}{2} \\ u_b^{l+1} &= u_0^{l+1} - \varphi_y^{l+1'} \frac{t^{l+1}}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. Kinematics of the adhesive shear angle.

and in the y -direction respectively

$$\begin{aligned} v_i^l &= v_0^l - \varphi_x^l \frac{t^l}{2} \\ v_b^{l+1} &= v_0^{l+1} + \varphi_x^{l+1} \frac{t^{l+1}}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Assuming small displacements, the rotation angles of the adhesive cross section can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{a,y}^l &= \frac{u_b^{l+1} - u_i^l}{\hat{t}_l} \\ &= \frac{1}{\hat{t}^l} \left(-u_0^l + u_0^{l+1} - \varphi_y^l \frac{t^l}{2} - \varphi_y^{l+1} \frac{t^{l+1}}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{a,x}^l &= \frac{v_i^l - v_b^{l+1}}{\hat{t}_l} \\ &= \frac{1}{\hat{t}^l} \left(v_0^l - v_0^{l+1} - \varphi_x^l \frac{t^l}{2} - \varphi_x^{l+1} \frac{t^{l+1}}{2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The shear stress in the adhesive is defined by

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_a^l = \mathbf{C}_a^l \cdot \boldsymbol{\gamma}_a^l \quad (10)$$

where

$$\mathbf{C}_a^l = G_a^l \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The shear strain is defined, just as for the structural layers, as the difference between the derivative of the vertical deflection and the cross section rotation of each adhesive layer.

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}_a^l = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{a,xz}^l \\ \gamma_{a,yz}^l \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{w}' - \boldsymbol{\varphi}'_a \quad (12)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}'_a = \begin{bmatrix} -\varphi_{a,y}^l \\ \varphi_{a,x}^l \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The stress state in the adhesive layer is therefore defined by the displacement field in the adjacent structural layers, which effectively couples the structural layers. Integration over the adhesive layer yields the adhesive layer stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_a^l . By varying the shear modulus of the adhesive, any state between uncoupled ($G_a = 0$) and directly coupled (large G_a) structural layers can be modelled.

2.3. Thermal load vectors

The temperature field is interpolated by assuming a bilinear in-plane temperature distribution and a quadratic distribution in the transverse direction. This choice is made to appropriately map the temperature field obtained from transient thermal simulations of the heat-pressing process of skis. For different applications, either fully quadratic or fully linear interpolations of the temperature field might be suitable. The temperature distribution in each layer can then be approximated by multiplying the thermal interpolation matrix with the nodal temperature vector.

$$\Delta T = \mathbf{B}_t^l \cdot \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} T_{i,0}^l \\ T_{i,1}^l \\ T_{i,2}^l \\ T_{j,0}^l \\ T_{j,1}^l \\ T_{j,2}^l \\ T_{k,0}^l \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}}_{\Theta^l} \quad (14)$$

Θ^l is the nodal temperature vector for the layer. $T_{i,0}^l$ is the temperature at node i on the layer l bottom surface, $T_{i,2}^l$ the temperature on the layer l top surface and $T_{i,1}^l$ is the temperature at the layer midsurface. The temperature at the top of layer l is assumed to be the same as at the bottom of layer $l + 1$ (hence a constant temperature is assumed through the thickness of the adhesive layers). The interpolation matrix is constructed from the standard bilinear interpolation functions $N_1 \dots N_4$ (Appendix B) in the natural coordinate frame and additional quadratic interpolation functions $H_0 \dots H_2$

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 &= \frac{1}{2} (-\zeta + \zeta^2) \\ H_1 &= 1 - \zeta^2 \\ H_2 &= \frac{1}{2} (\zeta + \zeta^2) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_l = [H_0 N_1 \quad H_1 N_1 \quad H_2 N_1 \quad H_0 N_2 \quad \dots]^T \quad (16)$$

Employing the standard procedures to interpolate the virtual strains yields the thermal load vector \mathbf{f}^l which consists of one part related to thermal membrane loads \mathbf{f}_m^l and one part related to thermal bending loads \mathbf{f}_b^l (integrals (5) and (6) in Eq. (5)).

$$\mathbf{f}^l = \mathbf{f}_m^l - \mathbf{f}_b^l \quad (17)$$

2.4. Finite element discretization and assembly

The vector of nodal values consists of the layer midsurface displacements U^l and V^l , the vertical deflection W and the layer rotational angles Φ_x^l and Φ_y^l , leading to a total of $4n + 1$ nodal DOF for a n -layer element.

$$\mathbf{v}_i = \begin{bmatrix} U_i^1 \\ \vdots \\ U_i^n \\ V_i^1 \\ \vdots \\ V_i^n \\ W_i \\ \Phi_{x,i}^1 \\ \vdots \\ \Phi_{x,i}^n \\ \Phi_{y,i}^1 \\ \vdots \\ \Phi_{y,i}^n \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

All layers are formulated in local natural coordinates and mapped to the global Cartesian coordinate system using standard isoparametric mapping techniques [25] (Fig. 3).

The shear strains in both the structural and the adhesive layers are interpolated using the MITC4 (mixed interpolation of tensorial components, Ref. [22]) formulation. In the MITC procedure, the shear strains are interpolated from the section rotations and the vertical deflection evaluated at tying points (A-D) which lie on the midpoint of each element edge.

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{\xi z} &= \frac{1}{2} (1 + \eta) \gamma_{\xi z}^A + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \eta) \gamma_{\xi z}^C \\ \gamma_{\eta z} &= \frac{1}{2} (1 + \xi) \gamma_{\eta z}^D + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \xi) \gamma_{\eta z}^B \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

This procedure effectively prevents shear locking. The adhesive layer's contribution leads to coupling terms in the element stiffness matrix that link the nodal DOF of adjacent layers.

Fig. 3. Four node element in cartesian coordinate system and mapped element in the natural coordinate system.

To obtain the stiffness matrices, second order Gaussian quadrature is used to integrate over the x - and y -direction, while integration over the thickness of each layer is carried out exactly. The total virtual work for one element in discretized form is

$$\delta W^{(e)} = \delta \mathbf{v}^{(e)T} \cdot [\mathbf{K}_{total}^{(e)} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{(e)} - \mathbf{f}^{(e)}] = 0 \quad (20)$$

with

$$\mathbf{K}_{total}^{(e)} = \mathbf{K}_a^{(e)} + \mathbf{K}_m^{(e)} + \mathbf{K}_b^{(e)} + \mathbf{K}_s^{(e)} \quad (21)$$

where each element stiffness matrix is the sum of the contributions of each layer

$$\mathbf{K}_i^{(e)} = \sum_{l=1}^n \mathbf{K}_i^l \quad \text{for } i \in \{m, b, s\} \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_a^{(e)} = \sum_{l=1}^{n-1} \mathbf{K}_a^l \quad (23)$$

and

$$\mathbf{f}^{(e)} = \sum_{l=1}^n \mathbf{f}^l \quad (24)$$

Finally, the finite element equation can be formed

$$\mathbf{K}_{total}^{(e)} \cdot \mathbf{v}^{(e)} = \mathbf{f}^{(e)} \quad (25)$$

3. Numerical examples

To assess the accuracy and applicability of the proposed LW-VISPE4 element, a series of numerical examples are presented. The objectives of these examples are: (i) to verify the correctness and convergence of the formulation, (ii) to demonstrate its ability to capture the effects of adhesive layer properties, and (iii) to illustrate its practical applicability and efficiency in comparison with three-dimensional SM.

The first example considers a three layer clamped plate and is used to verify the formulation against a high-fidelity three-dimensional SM. The comparison focuses on the maximum vertical deflection induced by a predefined temperature field. The second example presents a parametric study in which the adhesive stiffness and thickness are varied. This test illustrates the element's ability to represent any state from unbonded to fully bonded behaviour and highlights the influence of adhesive compliance and total thickness on global deformation. Finally, a multilayer geometry inspired by an alpine ski is analysed to demonstrate the capability of the formulation in predicting thermally induced deformations of highly heterogeneous layer stacks. This example also serves to compare the computational efficiency of the LW and three-dimensional SM approaches in terms of DOF and runtime.

3.1. Verification and convergence

A clamped plate with unconstrained transversal contraction is considered (for any nodes on $x = 0$ the nodal values U , Φ_y and W are zero and for the node on $x = y = 0$, V is set to zero as well). The plate is made up of an aluminium bottom, a steel top and a thick wooden core layer. The material properties and layer thicknesses are given in Table 1.

In the SM, the adhesive layer is modelled as an orthotropic material and assigned the respective adhesive shear modulus in the xz - and yz -plane and a negligibly low shear modulus in the xy -plane ($G_{xy} = 1 \times 10^{-6}$ MPa). To prevent transverse deformation of the adhesive layers, the Young's modulus is set to a high value in the z -direction ($E_z = 1 \times 10^6$ MPa) and very low values in the x - and y -directions ($E_x = E_y = 1 \times 10^{-6}$ MPa). The Poisson ratio is set to zero in all directions. The plate has a width b of 40 mm and a length L of 200 mm (Fig. 4). The element formulation is implemented in a Matlab [26] code and the results are compared to those obtained with a SM simulation performed in Ansys Mechanical [27], using quadrilateral elements with quadratic shape functions (SOLID186) (Fig. 5).

The maximum vertical deflection of the clamped plate subjected to a thermal load is studied for different element edge lengths. A constant thickness of 0.1 mm and a shear modulus $G_a = 170$ MPa are assigned to both adhesive layers. The thermal load is defined by

$$\Delta T(x, z) = -\hat{T} \left(1 - \frac{x}{2L} \right) \left(\frac{(z - t_{tot}/2)^2}{(t_{tot}/2)^2} - 1 \right) \quad (26)$$

with t_{tot} being the total thickness of the composite, $\hat{T} = 50^\circ\text{C}$ and the bottom of layer 1 lying on $z = 0$. This constitutes a parabolic temperature distribution through the thickness, with the top and bottom temperature difference being 0, and the maximum temperature at the center linearly decreasing from 50°C at the clamped end to 25°C at the free end. Due

Table 1

Layout and material properties of the studied 3-layer plate.

l	Material	t [mm]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	α [1/K]
1	Aluminium	1	71,000	0.33	2.3×10^{-5}
2	Wood	3	9680	0.4	4×10^{-6}
3	Steel	1	200,000	0.3	1.25×10^{-5}

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Comparison of the mesh using LW-VISPE4 elements (a) and solid elements (b), both with an edge length of 5 mm.

Fig. 5. Detail of the solid element mesh with an edge length of 2 mm and an adhesive layer thickness of 0.1 mm.

to the different coefficients of thermal expansion of the aluminium and steel layers, this leads to a vertical deflection of the plate (Fig. 6). For element edge lengths exceeding the layer thickness, each layer is discretized with a single element through the thickness. The wood layer is modelled with two, three, and six elements through the thickness for edge lengths of 2, 1, and 0.5 mm, respectively, while the top and bottom layers use one element through the thickness in all cases except for the smallest edge length, where two elements are used. The results show

Fig. 6. Plot of the vertical deflection w (a) and the horizontal displacement in x -direction u (b) of the clamped three-layer plate subjected to the specified thermal load with an element edge length of 10 mm. The results are shown for the mid-surfaces of each layer.

Table 2

Maximum vertical deflection of the clamped plate modelled with solid elements and LW-VISPE4 elements subjected to a thermal load for different element sizes.

Edge length [mm]	Vertical deflection [mm]	
	SM	LW-VISPE4
10	0.6611	0.6663
5	0.6607	0.6658
4	0.6607	0.6657
2	0.6607	0.6655
1	0.6609	0.6654
0.5	0.6606	0.6654

that the solution converges in both cases and changes in the solution are negligible for element edge lengths below 5 mm (Table 2). The proposed element formulation gives similar results to the SM simulation. An edge length of 5 mm leads to 8187 nodes and 24,561 DOF for the SM and 369 nodes and 4797 DOF for the plate model.

3.2. Effects of adhesive layer properties

The proposed element distinguishes itself from existing approaches primarily by incorporating the adhesive layers in the formulation with their mechanically relevant properties, the adhesive layer's thickness and the shear modulus. The effect of these two parameters on the composite's stiffness is studied in this section by considering the clamped plate configuration previously introduced. To assess the bending stiffness for the unbonded (no adhesive stiffness) case, instead of the thermal load, a vertical force of 10 N is applied to the free end of the plate. The adhesive layer thickness is varied from 0.05 to 0.2 mm. The results are again compared to those obtained from a SM simulation. An element edge length of 2 mm is used in both cases. The shear modulus is varied from 1.7×10^{-6} MPa to 1.7×10^6 MPa. The results are shown in Fig. 7. The deflection calculated with the new plate formulation correlates well with the results obtained from the SM. For low shear modulus values, the vertical deflection converges to a value of 14.6 mm. This value is not affected by the adhesive layer's thickness, since in this configuration, the

Fig. 7. Influence of the adhesive layer's thickness and shear modulus on the laminates stiffness.

Table 3

Vertical deflection of the clamped plate with a vertical force of 10 N applied at the free end for bonded and unbonded ($G_a = 1.7 \times 10^{-6}$ MPa and 1.7×10^6 MPa respectively) laminates with thin and thick ($\hat{t} = 0.05$ mm and 0.2 mm respectively) adhesive layers.

\hat{t} [mm]	Unbonded		Bonded	
	SM	LW-VISPE4	SM	LW-VISPE4
0.05	14.5684	14.5849	0.7024	0.6960
0.20	14.5683	14.5859	0.6138	0.6081

Table 4

Layup and material properties of the studied dummy ski. (UHMWPE: Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene, GFRP: Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer).

l	Material	t [mm]	E [MPa]	ν [-]	α [1/K]
1	UHMWPE	1.5	1750	0.4	2×10^{-4}
2	GFRP	0.4	24,500	0.36	1×10^{-5}
3	Aluminium	0.6	71,000	0.33	1.25×10^{-5}
4	Wood	8	9680	0.4	4×10^{-6}
5	GFRP	0.4	24,500	0.36	1×10^{-5}
6	Aluminium	0.4	71,000	0.33	1.25×10^{-5}
7	Polyamid	0.6	1300	0.4	1.45×10^{-4}

Table 5

Comparison of the maximum vertical deflection, computation times and DOF with the proposed element formulation and a SM finite element simulation.

Method	Deflection [mm]	Time [s]	DOF
Solid Model	0.3339	44.0	63,063
LW-VISPE4	0.3275	4.3	10,701

total bending stiffness is only the sum of all layer bending stiffnesses. For high adhesive shear modulus values, the solutions each converge to different deflections. A thicker adhesive layer leads to a higher bending stiffness of the laminate, and therefore less vertical deflection (Table 3). In between these two limit cases, the laminates with thicker adhesive layers exhibit a lower bending stiffness, than those with thinner adhesive layers. This can be attributed to two counteracting effects related to the adhesive layer thickness. A thicker adhesive layer leads to a larger second moment of inertia of the total structure by increasing the vertical distance between the structural layers. At the same time, the shear stiffness of the adhesive layer (G_a/\hat{t}) decreases.

3.3. Ski-like multilayer application

For the final assessment of the developed element formulation a clamped plate of the same dimensions as in the first example is considered, but with a more complex layup inspired by a typical alpine ski (Table 4).

This example is chosen because it closely resembles the intended application of the element formulation, demonstrating its ability to efficiently capture the deformation behaviour of individual layers bonded by adhesive under thermal loading. All adhesive layers are modelled with a thickness of 0.1 mm and a shear modulus of $G_a = 170$ MPa. A parabolic through-thickness temperature distribution is applied, with a temperature increase of $\Delta T = 50$ °C at the top and bottom surfaces and $\Delta T = 0$ °C at the mid-plane, given by

$$\Delta T(z) = \hat{T} \left(\frac{(z - t_{tot}/2)^2}{(t_{tot}/2)^2} \right) \tag{27}$$

In contrast to the first example, this temperature profile produces maximum thermal mismatch near the outer layers, thereby amplifying shear effects within the laminate. This loading represents a simplified

Fig. 8. Detail of the solid element mesh with an edge length of 5 mm and an adhesive layer thickness of 0.1 mm.

temperature profile that may arise during the heating phase of a multi-layer structure in a press. An element edge length of 5 mm is used for both the plate and the SM (Fig. 8). The calculations are performed on one CPU core; the hardware specification is given in Appendix C. Table 5 summarizes the resulting maximum deflections, computation times and DOF for both models, highlighting the computational efficiency of the proposed formulation. The maximum deflection is evaluated at the coordinates $x = 200$ mm and $y = 20$ mm. For the SM, the average displacement over the plate thickness at this location is taken as the reference value. Fig. 9 shows the transverse displacement of the free end in the x - z plane at the same coordinates for both models. The LW-VISPE4 element accurately captures the deformation response induced by the non-uniform thermal loading. The combination of varying coefficients of thermal expansion and the imposed temperature gradient leads to pronounced

Fig. 9. Displacement of the free end in the x - z plane at coordinates $x = 200$ mm and $y = 20$ mm, obtained from the SM and LW-VISPE4 simulations. Note that the horizontal lines are included solely as a visual aid to distinguish the layers and do not represent the deformed shape of the structure.

shear deformations within the structural layers. Neglecting these shear effects would result in unrealistically high shear strains in the adhesive layers and thus an overestimation of the global bending stiffness. This demonstrates the necessity of a Reissner–Mindlin formulation at the layer level for the intended application. For thin, adhesively bonded layers with negligible transverse shear deformation, a Kirchhoff–Love formulation may still provide an adequate approximation.

4. Conclusions

A novel layerwise plate element has been developed for the efficient simulation of adhesively bonded multilayer structures subjected to thermal loading. The formulation accounts for shear deformation in both the structural layers and the adhesive interfaces, the latter being represented as shear-only layers with explicitly defined thickness and stiffness. In contrast to many existing LW formulations, this approach enables the adhesive layer's mechanical influence to be captured without the need to model it as an additional plate layer, thereby reducing the number of DOF. Thermal strains are incorporated at the layer level. Validation against three-dimensional solid finite element reference models demonstrated good agreement with the computed deflections, while requiring substantially fewer DOF. These results confirm that the proposed element provides a computationally efficient alternative to full three-dimensional solid modelling for bonded multilayer plates.

The formulation is not without limitations. As with all plate-based approaches, local three-dimensional effects such as detailed edge stresses cannot be captured. Normal stress in the through-thickness direction is neglected in both structural and adhesive layers, making the element unsuitable for predicting delamination phenomena. Additionally, the current implementation assumes a constant adhesive shear modulus. In practical applications, adhesive stiffness may vary with time and temperature, for instance during curing. Since the shear modulus enters the formulation as a parameter, such behaviour could be incorporated at the constitutive and algorithmic level without modifying the finite element formulation itself. While evaluation of stress distributions could provide additional insight, the present example focuses on kinematic accuracy and global stiffness. Detailed stress recovery, particularly for transverse and interfacial stresses, is therefore left for future work.

Despite these limitations, the inclusion of adhesive compliance and thickness distinguishes the LW-VISPE4 element from existing LW formulations. It is particularly suitable for applications where the global deformation behaviour of bonded multilayer structures is of primary interest and where computational efficiency is essential, such as in parametric studies or iterative design investigations. Future work will therefore focus on the application of the proposed formulation to the simulation of cure-induced deformations in manufacturing processes of multilayer structures. For this purpose, the developed element formulation can be implemented in an iterative, sequentially coupled thermo-mechanical solution algorithm with a temperature and time dependent adhesive shear modulus, as proposed in Ref. [17].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

D. von Burg: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.
R. Baumann: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT to enhance the readability and language of the manuscript. After utilizing this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Appendix A. Elasticity matrices

$$\mathbf{C}^l = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x^l}{1 - \nu_{xy}^l \nu_{yx}^l} & \nu_{xy}^l \frac{E_y^l}{1 - \nu_{xy}^l \nu_{yx}^l} & 0 \\ \nu_{xy}^l \frac{E_y^l}{1 - \nu_{xy}^l \nu_{yx}^l} & \frac{E_y^l}{1 - \nu_{xy}^l \nu_{yx}^l} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy}^l \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\mathbf{C}_s^l = \begin{bmatrix} G_{xz} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{yz} \end{bmatrix}$$

Appendix B. Shape functions

The element is derived in the natural coordinate system spanned by ξ , η and ζ . Four bilinear interpolation functions are used to interpolate the displacements and rotations between the element nodes.

$$\begin{aligned} N_1 &= \frac{1}{4} (1 + \xi) (1 + \eta) \\ N_2 &= \frac{1}{4} (1 - \xi) (1 + \eta) \\ N_3 &= \frac{1}{4} (1 - \xi) (1 - \eta) \\ N_4 &= \frac{1}{4} (1 + \xi) (1 - \eta) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Appendix C. Hardware

- Processor: Intel® Xeon™ W-2275, 3.30 GHz, 14 Cores
- RAM: 128 GB
- SSD: SK hynix SC401 SATA 512 GB

Data availability statement

All input data required to reproduce the results presented in this paper are provided within the manuscript. The finite element code developed and used for the analyses is proprietary and is not publicly available.

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